

THE HISTORIOGRAPHY OF STUDYING THE HISTORY OF ARCHAEOLOGICAL MONUMENTS LOCATED IN THE NORTHERN PART OF THE REPUBLIC OF KARAKALPAKSTAN

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Abstract. Archeology is a science that studies the history of mankind on the basis of ancient sources and memories. The peoples of Dune have a history stretching back several thousand years. However, from the last five to six thousand years of this long historical development, there are only written works of art, and before that there were no writings and written history in the nations.

Keywords: agriculture, on-line works, archeology, Aral Sea, Red Sands, Khorezm culture.

ИСТОРИОГРАФИЯ ИЗУЧЕНИЯ ИСТОРИИ АРХЕОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ПАМЯТНИКОВ, РАСПОЛОЖЕННЫХ В СЕВЕРНОЙ ЧАСТИ РЕСПУБЛИКИ КАРАКАЛПАКСТАН

Аннотация. Археология – это наука, изучающая историю человечества на основе древних источников и воспоминаний. Народы Дюны имеют историю, насчитывающую несколько тысячелетий. Однако из последних пяти-шести тысяч лет этого длительного исторического развития существуют только письменные произведения искусства, а до этого письмен и письменной истории у народов не было.

Ключевые слова: земледелие, он-лайн работы, археология, Аральское море, Красные пески, Хорезмская культура.

INTRODUCTION

Many scientists are interested in the territory of Central Asia, most of them have seen these lands with their own eyes, most of them have commented on the works of the people they saw, and in their one-line works, they have written its history, memories and historical terms x. b wrote down.

In the artistic works of Arab, Persian and Chinese authors written down in the Middle Ages, the settlements of the peoples located on the banks of Ámudarya, irrigation canals h. t. b. have information about. In the science of archeology, we will dwell on the works of scientists who are the source of the terms of the history of the territories and archeological memories of the three rasatatu under the name of Kerder culture. The latest Arab geographer Ibn-Khordabek, in his work "Countries and Roads", showed that Kardar was a part of Khorezm within the Eastern Arab Caliphate, and that Kardar Oblast was a separate territory. He recorded the Aral Sea as "Kurder Lakes" in 865.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

More information about Kerder can be found in the work of another Arab geographer, Ol'-Istakhridin, written in 930-933. Here we find that Kerderdi is clearly mentioned for the first time in the city account. It is located on the neck of the Kerder Canal in the same city. Al-Istakhri says that the relative location of Kerderdi is "Mizdakhan volost between Joyhun and

Kardar"- . A guide to the location of the city of Kerder is clearly written in the information on the relative location of the cities of Khorezm.

Compared to Al-Istakhridin's information about Kerder, we see more information in Al-Makdisidi's work entitled "Askhan-ot-Takasim fi-Marifat al-Akalim" written around 985. Al Mahdisi says that the city of Kerder is located on the right side of Ámudáre on the so-called "Haytal" side. Apart from that, Ol Makhdisi tells about one Kerder located on the left bank of Khorasannın. Kerder, on the side of Kerder Haytal, is relatively large in size, so it is mentioned that it was a strong fortress-city, and the city of Kerder is located on the bank of this canal.

Valuable information about Kerder was recorded by the Persian anonymous "Khudud oğil-Olam" and Ibn Yaquuttın in his work entitled "Kitab Mujam al-Ushbudun" in 1224. Yaqut says about Kerder: "The settlement of Kerder is located in the Khorezm region or on its border with the Turks," and says that the language of the people there is Khorezmshede, not Navkshede. There were many villages in these regions, and there were many goods and animals in them. However, these people were very open. Ibn-Kassan al-Haban told me about them.

RESULTS

Analyzing these data, the name Kerder b. e since the VIII century b. We know that there were three of them until the beginning of the 13th century. Including, based on the information in the sources, it was determined that the Kerder horse belongs to the identified area, the castle and the channel.

As for the Kerder region, we have enough information about its distribution in the sources listed above.

Based on the fact that Ibn Khordabek called the Aral Sea "Kerder Lakes", it was determined that the name of the sea (the name of the region) was named after the region on the coast of the island. So, based on the information given by Al-Makdisiy, Kerder village is located in the territory of this region, it is located on the side called Haital, which is the center of this region and is located on the right side of Ámudarya. According to Al-Istakhri, on the land of Kerder region, Mizdakhán region is located between Kerder and Joyhun above the city of Galma-Galwir. (in which the word is said about the channel). There is no doubt that the Kerder Canal and the Kerder Region are located on the right bank of the Ámudarya.

DISCUSSION

New archeological researches clearly demarcate the existence of a separate culture in this territory, distinct from Khorezm culture, and even its dispersed territory. The dispersed region of this culture is bordered by the Aral Sea to the north of the Kerder region, Ámudarya to the west, and the Red Sands to the east.

In conclusion, the written sources about Kerder raise the issue of conducting archaeological research, mapping this territory, reexamining the canals and human settlements here. Concluding from the above, we have a picture of the existence of the city named Kerder, the canal region, from the 8th century to the 13th century. Reviewing the information about the canal, we learned that the banks of the passed through the old banks and that it operated until the 9th and 10th centuries. This channel is connected with the lower branch of the current Shortanbay area.

CONCLUSIONS

Due to the archeological research conducted in recent years, the archeological map of these lands and the names of many memorials and geographical places have been identified in the written sources of medieval authors. He informed about the land of Darsan belonging to this Kerder culture, quoting Makdisi, "Darsan - Tók city gray Kerder is one day's journey. This corresponds to approximately 30-49 kilometers," he wrote. Khayvan city, that is, the city of Kerder, is located in the territory of the current Kerder farm just above the raised fence. Makdisi continued the information: "It is one day's journey from Mizdakhkhan to Vardarag, and from Vardarag to Kerderge, you will walk for one day," i.e. 30-40 km. Vardarag fund can be placed on Qiraan hill.

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